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COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

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Engine performance using FPBO

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

A single-cylinder engine test bench is recently built at Biomass Technology Group B.V. (BTG). In this report, experimental studies are carried out to investigate engine performance using Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (FPBO). Diesel and FPBO+E10 (FPBO blended with 10 wt% ethanol) are tested at a wide range of operating conditions. Fuel consumption and exhaust emission are measured. Based on the needle lift, fuel pressure, and cylinder pressure data, a set of indicators are defined to evaluate fuel injection and combustion characteristics.

Results show that for the same settings of the mechanical inline pump, FPBO+E10 shows an almost doubled injection duration, slightly advanced injection timing, and higher injection pressure than diesel. The autoignition of FPBO+E10 requires a high in-cylinder temperature, e.g., by heating the intake air temperature to 125 °C or higher. The ignition delay of FPBO+E10 is close to that of diesel, while the burn duration of FPBO+E10 is much shorter. For the single-cylinder engine running on FPBO+E10, the optimized engine net indicated efficiency is 53.6%, and the indicated specific fuel consumption is 373 g/kW·h. However, the maximum brake efficiency is just 21.8% due to parasitic losses. Generally, FPBO+E10 has comparable emission levels with diesel. At the intake temperature of 125 °C, FPBO+E10 has slightly higher CO and HC emissions but around half the NO_x emissions compared to diesel operation.

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Terminology

Abbreviation	Description
AHRR	Apparent heat release rate
BD	Burn duration
BTG	Biomass Technology Group B.V.
CHP	Combined heat and power
COV	Coefficient of variance
CP	Combustion phasing
EOC	End of combustion
EOI	End of injection
FPBO	Fast pyrolysis bio-oil
ID	Ignition delay
InjD	Injection duration
MEP IMEP gIMEP nIMEP BMEP	Mean effective pressure Indicated mean effective pressure Gross IMEP Net IMEP Brake mean effective pressure
MFB	Mass fraction burned
SCR	Selective catalytic reduction
SOC	Start of combustion
SOI	Start of injection
TDC	Top dead center

1. Introduction

Renewable fuels produced from thermal processing (torrefaction, pyrolysis, and gasification) play an important role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and curbing climate change. Pyrolysis oil is a condensate of the organic vapor released from thermal processing of base material. Owing to the high energy density, extensive research is being conducted to produce and utilize pyrolysis oil. Typically, the feedstocks for pyrolysis plants are organic substances such as biomass (residues from forestry and agriculture) and organic waste (plastics, tires, and household waste).

In the EU funded SmartCHP project, the so-called fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) is used for combined heat and power (CHP) applications. The biomass feedstocks are first heated rapidly to 450–600 °C in the absence of oxygen. After a short residence time of around 2 seconds, the formed vapor is quickly condensed to a liquid, i.e., FPBO. The short residence time in reactor and condenser makes fast pyrolysis an efficient way to convert solid biomass to liquid biofuel.

A diesel genset engine combines good dynamic performance with a high thermal efficiency, so it is used as the electricity generator in the SmartCHP system. However, the physicochemical properties of FPBO are quite different from commercial diesel, which makes its direct application on diesel engines very challenging:

- FPBO has high acidity and high water content, which is prone to corroding the steel materials in fuel supply and injection system.
- The low fluidity of FPBO (high viscosity) may choke up the pump.
- FPBO has some particle content, which may result in nozzle clogging during injection. Its polymerization tendency at elevated temperature aggravates nozzle clogging further.
- The heating value of FPBO is lower than that of diesel due to its high oxygen content. Its volumetric lower heating value (LHV) is around half that of diesel.
- FPBO has low chemical reactivity (cetane number of around 5 – 25), and hence it is usually hard to (auto) ignite in conventional diesel engines.

Therefore, the following measures should be taken when implementing engine modifications:

- Corrosion-resistant materials like stainless steel are necessary for all pumps, injectors and tubes which have direct contact with FPBO.
- Appropriate fuel preheating is required to reduce fuel viscosity, while the fuel temperature should not exceed 60 °C to avoid polymerization.
- Special consideration should be made in the design of FPBO injector, including materials, treatment process, number of nozzle orifices, diameter of nozzle orifices, etc.
- To facilitate FPBO autoignition, engine compression ratio needs to be elevated, and in most cases, intake preheating is still necessary.

Although it is promising to modify a diesel engine for pure FPBO, in most of existing experimental studies, FPBO is blended with alcohols and high reactivity fuels [1–6]. The mass fraction of FPBO is generally below 30%. Just a few studies from

Biomass Technology Group B.V. (BTG) achieve a higher FPBO content (>70%) in their modified diesel engine [7,8].

Therefore, one of the main challenges in SmartCHP project is to develop a prototype engine running on FPBO. Recently, a single-cylinder engine test bench was commissioned at BTG. The project milestone, running an engine on FPBO for over 500 hours, was achieved in this engine test bench without the need to overhaul the fuel injection system [9]. In this report, follow-up experimental studies are performed to investigate engine performance using FPBO. Section 2 introduces the experimental methodology, including engine modifications, data post-processing methods, and test conditions. Then, the results are presented and discussed in Section 3. Finally, the general conclusions are detailed in Section 4.

2. Methodology

2.1 Single-cylinder diesel genset engine

Table 1 shows the specifications of the single-cylinder engine. It is modified from a 3-cylinder Baudouin 3M10 diesel genset engine. Only 1 cylinder runs with the specific fuel and the other 2 cylinders are disabled by puncturing the pistons. The rotational speed of this engine is fixed at 1500 rpm. A 4-pole Linz SLT18 MD generator is installed to convert engine crankshaft power to electrical power output, and several electric heaters are used as electrical loads.

Table 1. Engine specifications.

Parameter	Value
Base engine	Baudouin 3M10G
Stroke	120 mm
Bore	105 mm
Displacement	1.04 L
Compression ratio	17.6
Rotational speed	1500 rpm
Aspiration	Natural aspiration
Fuel system	Mechanical pump
Nozzle holes	5
Nozzle diameter	250 μ m
Nozzle umbrella angle	142°

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the experimental engine setup.

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the experimental engine setup. During experiments, the engine starts with commercial EN590 diesel, then changes to a 'rinsing fuel' (n-butanol) for 3 minutes, and switches to test fuels (FPBO and its blends). After that the dedicated experiments, it changes to rinsing fuel, and finally switches back to diesel before engine shutdown. Due to the special properties of FPBO, major modifications are implemented to the fuel supply and injection system. 3 fuel tanks contain the engine startup, test, and rinse fuels, respectively. A stirrer is installed in the test fuel tank to inhibit phase separation. The mass of the test fuel tank is measured by a balance (TELL EAG-80) and the fuel consumption rate is calculated through recording the weight of fuel tank. Since the viscosity of FPBO is much higher than that of diesel, a fuel preheater can heat the fuel to 40–60 °C to reduce fuel viscosity. A dual-circuit fuel injector is designed in-house for the FPBO injection. The original inline pump is used to pressurize the working fluid (diesel) in the control circuit to 300 bar. A pressurizer, which is integrated into the mechanical injector, has a floating plunger to deliver the high pressure from the control fluid to the test fuel. The pump, injector and tubes which are in contact with FPBO are made of stainless steel. Any direct contact of FPBO with original engine parts is avoided by adopting such a dual-circuit injector. The opening pressure of the mechanical injector is adjusted to around 130 bar. The injector nozzle has 5 orifices with a diameter of 250 μm and an umbrella angle of 142°. The nozzle needle is made of ceramic material (silicon nitride) for maximum durability.

Table 2. Sensors installed on the engine test bench.

Sensor	Symbol	Type	Inaccuracy
Intake mass flow	\dot{m}_{intake}	Bosch hot-film air-mass meter, type 0280217107	± 1%
Intake temperature	P_{intake}	Thermocouple, type K	± 0.75%
Exhaust temperature	$T_{exhaust}$	Thermocouple, type K	± 0.75%
Fuel temperature	T_{fuel}	Thermocouple, type K	± 0.75%
Cylinder pressure	P	AE Sensors AE-SML-20.0-0400B	± 0.5%
Fuel injection pressure	$P_{injection}$	AE Sensors AE-SML-20.0-0400B	± 0.5%
Needle lift	L_{needle}	Balluff BAW000N	± 8 μm
CO ^(a)	$X_{[CO]}$	Testo 350	± 25 ppm
H ₂	$X_{[H2]}$		± 5 ppm
NO	$X_{[NO]}$		± 5 ppm
NO ₂	$X_{[NO2]}$		± 5 ppm
SO ₂	$X_{[SO2]}$		± 5 ppm
HC ^(b)	$X_{[HC]}$	Brain Bee AGS-200	± 5 ppm

^(a) The electrochemical sensor of CO generally responds to both CO and H₂. Testo 350 employs a cross-compensating CO sensor to negate H₂ interference.

^(b) Emissions of hydrocarbons (HC) are measured as hexane (C₆H₁₄).

To facilitate FPBO autoignition, the engine compression ratio is elevated from 15.5 to 17.6, and an air preheater is installed to preheat the intake charge to any value between 50 and 200 °C. The intake mass flow, intake temperature, and exhaust temperature are measured and recorded. A Heidenhain ROD-420-3600 rotary encoder is installed, and a Picoscope 4423 PC oscilloscope is used to collect signals

from cylinder pressure, fuel pressure, and needle lift sensors at a 0.1-crank angle interval. The types and inaccuracies of the sensors are shown in Table 2. The Testo 350 emission tester is used to measure the volume fraction of O₂, CO₂, CO, H₂, NO, NO₂, and SO₂ in exhaust gas, and the hydrocarbons (HC) are measured by the Brain Bee AGS-200 emission tester.

2.2 Data post-processing and definitions of engine related parameters

2.2.1 Cylinder pressure traces

Cylinder pressure traces are important to investigate the in-cylinder combustion processes. Figure 2(a) shows the crank angle resolved cylinder pressure data from 125 successive engine cycles. The 0-degree crank angle (°CA) is defined as the top dead center (TDC) at the end of the compression stroke. The pressure data is presented using a logarithmic y-axis to highlight the fluctuations during the intake and exhaust strokes. For noise reduction, the cylinder pressure data from the measurement of 125 engine cycles are first ensemble averaged and then filtered through a first-order Savitzky-Golay filter with a sliding window of 6.1 °CA. Figure 2(b) shows an example of the processed cylinder pressure profile, where the four strokes are presented with different colors. The relationship between cylinder pressure and volume within one engine cycle is shown in Figure 2(c).

Figure 2. Cylinder pressure versus crank angle and P-V diagram.

2.2.2 Needle lift and fuel pressure

The needle lift of the mechanical injector and the fuel pressure are measured to investigate fuel injection characteristics. Limited by the inline pump, fuel injection timing can only be adjusted manually and imprecisely when the engine is shut down. Hence, the needle lift profile is important to determine the start and end of fuel injection. In this study, the start of injection (SOI) and end of injection (EOI) are defined as the moments when the needle rises and drops to 20% of the maximum lift, respectively. Consequently, the injection duration (InjD) is defined as the period between SOI and EOI.

Figure 3. Needle lift, fuel pressure, and cylinder pressure versus crank angle. Test condition: diesel fuel, intake temperature of 50 °C, brake load of 3.8 kW. Panel (a) shows the data in the crank angle range of -30 to 60 °CA. Panel (b) shows the magnified range between -20 to 10 °CA. In panel (b), the start of injection (SOI), end of injection (EOI), and injection duration (InjD) are presented. In both panels, cylinder pressure profiles are multiplied by 3 for better visibility.

Figure 3 shows an example of the needle lift and fuel pressure profiles running the setup on diesel at a brake load of 3.8 kW. The needle lifts when fuel pressure reaches around 130 bar and closes when fuel pressure starts to drop. The fuel pressure during injection is around 200–320 bar, which is also influenced by the engine load and fuel type.

2.2.3 Mean effective pressures

The energy conversion of an internal combustion engine starts from the chemical energy stored in the fuel and finally ends up with the mechanical output of the crankshaft. Figure 4 shows the engine energy flow map within one engine cycle (four strokes), i.e., 720 °CA. In engine research, the energy flows within one engine cycle are presented by so-called mean effective pressures (MEP), which is just a normalization by cylinder displacement to be able to compare different engines

more easily (see nomenclature in orange in Figure 4). Hence, the chemical energy contained in the injected fuel per cycle is expressed as the *FuelIMEP*:

$$FuelIMEP = \frac{m_{fuel} \times LHV_{fuel}}{V_d} \quad (1)$$

where m_{fuel} is injected fuel mass per cycle, LHV_{fuel} is the lower heating value of fuel, and V_d is the cylinder displacement.

Figure 4. Engine energy flow map and nomenclature.

The engine indicated mean effective pressures (IMEP) is determined from the P-V diagram shown in Figure 2(c). Depending on the bounds of the integral, the gross IMEP (*gIMEP*) and net IMEP (*nIMEP*) are calculated according to:

$$gIMEP = \frac{W_{gross}}{V_d} = \frac{\int_{-180^\circ}^{180^\circ} PdV}{V_d} \quad (2)$$

$$nIMEP = \frac{W_{net}}{V_d} = \frac{W_{gross} - W_{pump}}{V_d} = \frac{\int_{-360^\circ}^{360^\circ} PdV}{V_d} \quad (3)$$

where P and V refer to cylinder pressure and cylinder volume, respectively.

In this single-cylinder engine bench, the mechanical power of the crankshaft is used to drive the generator to produce electricity. Here, the electrical power output from the generator, i.e., the apparent power in the alternating current circuits, is treated as the engine brake load (the efficiency of the generator is assumed to be 100%). Hence, the brake mean effective pressure (*BMEP*) is determined as:

$$BMEP = \frac{Load}{V_d \times RPM / 60 / 2} \quad (4)$$

where *Load* is the electrical load (in the unit kW_e), and *RPM* is the engine rotational speed.

2.2.4 Efficiencies and emissions

Figure 4 also includes the definition of engine efficiencies. The relationships of the engine-related efficiencies are also presented in the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned} BMEP &= fuelMEP \cdot \eta_{brake} \\ &= fuelMEP \cdot \eta_{mechanical} \cdot \eta_{NIE} \\ &= fuelMEP \cdot \eta_{mechanical} \cdot \eta_{gas-exchange} \cdot \eta_{GIE} \\ &= fuelMEP \cdot \eta_{mechanical} \cdot \eta_{gas-exchange} \cdot \eta_{thermal} \cdot \eta_{combustion} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Engine brake efficiency, η_{brake} , is the ratio of *BMEP* and *fuelMEP*. However, this efficiency is relatively low and not representative due to the major modification, e.g., the friction losses from the punctured pistons in the two inactive cylinders. Therefore, the net indicated efficiency (η_{NIE}), which is the ratio of *nIMEP* and *fuelMEP*, is used to evaluate the efficiencies of in-cylinder processes in this study. The engine operation condition has negligible influence on the mechanical efficiency ($\eta_{mechanical}$), so it can be treated as constant. The gross indicated efficiency (η_{GIE}) is the ratio of η_{NIE} and $\eta_{gas-exchange}$. The determination of combustion efficiency ($\eta_{combustion}$) relies on the measured emission data (see Table 2), while the thermal efficiency ($\eta_{thermal}$) is calculated from the ratio of η_{GIE} and $\eta_{combustion}$. Combustion efficiency is determined as:

$$\eta_{Combustion} = \left(1 - \frac{IS_{HC} \times LHV_{fuel} + IS_{CO} \times LHV_{CO} + IS_{H_2} \times LHV_{H_2}}{IS_{FC} \times LHV_{fuel}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $IS_{[X]}$ and $IS_{[FC]}$ ¹ are the indicated specific emissions and indicated specific fuel consumption (both in the unit g/kWh), respectively. $IS_{[FC]}$ and $IS_{[X]}$ are determined as follows.

¹ $IS_{[X]}$ and $IS_{[FC]}$ here are both based on the net indicated power. Caution should be taken when comparing them with the emission standards which are generally based on the brake power.

$$IS_{FC} = \frac{Flow_{fuel} \times 10^3}{Power_{net}} \quad (7)$$

$$IS_{[X]} = \frac{(Flow_{air} + Flow_{fuel}) \times 10^3 \times [X] \times 10^{-6} \times MW_X}{MW_{exhaust} \times Power_{net}} \quad (8)$$

where $[X]$ refers to the volume fraction of a gaseous emission in ppm, $Flow_{air}$ and $Flow_{fuel}$ are the mass flow rates of air and fuel in kg/h respectively, MW_X is the molar weight of the species X , $MW_{exhaust}$ is determined with the assumption of completely combustion, and $Power_{net}$ in kW is calculated from the net indicated work in one engine cycle as follows.

$$Power_{net} = \frac{W_{net} \times RPM}{60 \times 2 \times 1000} \quad (9)$$

It is noted that the measured NO emission is converted to NO₂ when determining NO_x emission. This is because the transformation of NO to NO₂ under ambient conditions is fast.

2.2.5 Engine heat release analysis

Engine heat release analysis is an important diagnostic tool to investigate fuel ignition and combustion characteristics, which aids in optimizing engine performance. Crank-angle-based engine cylinder pressure (P) data can be used to implement engine heat-release rate analysis according to the first law of thermodynamics.

$$\frac{dQ_{chem}}{d\theta} + h_f \frac{dm_f}{d\theta} = P \frac{dV}{d\theta} + \frac{dQ_{ht}}{d\theta} + mc_v \frac{dT}{d\theta} \quad (10)$$

where Q_{chem} is the chemical energy released from combustion reaction, θ is the crank angle, Q_{ht} is the energy loss due to heat transfer to the cylinder wall, m_f is the mass of injected fuel and h_f is the sensible enthalpy of the fuel. m , c_v , and T are the mass, mean specific heat capacity at constant volume, and mean temperature of the cylinder charge, respectively. The second term in left-hand side can be neglected since h_f is negligible.

The apparent heat-release rate (AHRR) is defined as the net heat-release rate without considering the energy loss rate due to heat transfer.

$$AHRR = \frac{dQ_n}{d\theta} = \frac{dQ_{chem}}{d\theta} - \frac{dQ_{ht}}{d\theta} = P \frac{dV}{d\theta} + mc_v \frac{dT}{d\theta} \quad (11)$$

With the uniform ideal gas assumption, the AHRR can be determined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 AHRR &= p \frac{dV}{d\theta} + mc_v \frac{dT}{d\theta} \\
 &= \left(1 + \frac{c_v}{R}\right) p \frac{dV}{d\theta} + \frac{c_v}{R} V \frac{dp}{d\theta} \\
 &= \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} p \frac{dV}{d\theta} + \frac{1}{\gamma-1} V \frac{dp}{d\theta}
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where R is the so-called specific gas constant (J/kg/K). It equals the difference of specific heat capacities at constant pressure and constant volume ($c_p - c_v$) by definition. γ is the specific heat ratio, c_p/c_v .

Figure 5. Cylinder pressure, AHRR, MFB, and cumulated AHRR versus crank angle. Test condition: diesel fuel, intake temperature of 50 °C, brake load of 3.8 kW. Panel (a) shows the start and end of injection. Panel (b) presents CA10, CA50, CA90, ignition delay (ID), and burn duration (BD).

The mass fraction burned (MFB) is defined as the integral of AHRR normalized by the total net heat release within one engine cycle,

$$MFB = \frac{\int_{-360^\circ}^{\theta} AHRR d\theta}{\int_{-360^\circ}^{360^\circ} AHRR d\theta} \quad (13)$$

Figure 5 shows an example of AHRR and MFB profiles using diesel at brake load of 3.8 kW. The cumulated AHRR indicates the apparent heat released from combustion reaction.

In this work, the start of combustion (SOC), combustion phasing (CP), and end of combustion (EOC) is defined as the crank angle where MFB reaches 10% (CA10), 50% (CA50), and 90% (CA90), respectively. Based on them, the ignition delay (ID) is defined as the period between SOI and SOC (i.e., CA10 - SOI), and the burn duration is defined as the period between SOC and EOC (i.e., CA90 - CA10) as shown in Figure 5. These indicators are used to characterize the ignition and combustion processes, and their definitions are listed in

Table 3.

Table 3. Definitions of indicators

Indicator	Full name	Definition
SOI	Start of injection	The moment when the needle rises to 20% of the maximum lift
EOI	End of injection	The moment when the needle drops to 20% of the maximum lift
SOC	Start of combustion	The moment when MFB reaches 10% (CA10)
CP	Combustion phasing	The moment when MFB reaches 50% (CA50)
EOC	End of combustion	The moment when MFB reaches 90% (CA90)
InjD	Injection duration	The period between SOI and EOI
ID	Ignition delay	The period between SOI and SOC
BD	Burn duration	The period between SOC and EOC

2.3 Tested fuels and conditions

In engine experiments, EN590 diesel is used as reference fuel, n-butanol is used as rinse fuel, and FPBO with addition of 10 wt.% ethanol (FPBO+E10) is the tested fuel. The properties of these fuels are shown in Table 4.

The influence of intake temperature, electrical load, and injection timing are also investigated. Table 5 shows the experimental conditions. Injection timing plays an important role in engine combustion and emission performance. Three injection timings are implemented by manually adjusting the mechanical inline pump to 3 different positions.

The electrical load is controlled by a load bank. The rated power of the unmodified 3-cylinder engine is 30 kW_e, so the theoretical rated power of the modified single-cylinder engine could be 10 kW_e. However, in practice, it is found that the maximum electrical load for stable operation on diesel is 6 kW_e, and the maximum load drops to 3.8 kW_e for FPBO+E10. The possible causes for derating are as follows:

- The other two cylinders which are disabled by puncturing the pistons still produce considerable friction loss.

- Our modifications may lead to an imperfectly balanced crank shaft which limits the maximum load.
- The camshaft timing (intake/exhaust valve timings) is not optimized after modification.
- The intake preheating reduces the air mass flow from natural aspiration.

Hence, as shown in Table 5, the electrical load varies between 0–6 kW_e for diesel combustion and 0–3.8 kW_e for FPBO+E10 combustion.

To test FPBO+E10, the engine is first operated on diesel at 2 kW_e, and then the intake temperature is elevated from 50 to 125 °C. After that, the fuel supply system switches to rinse fuel (n-butanol) and finally to FPBO+E10. For diesel combustion, the intake preheating is unnecessary since it may lead to higher fuel consumption rate. Therefore, the intake temperature for diesel tests is changed in the range of 50–125 °C. However, for FPBO combustion, the low intake temperature could result in wall wetting of the engine cylinder due to the prolonged ignition delay, which is prone to forming gum-like deposits on the cylinder wall and results in engine damage. Furthermore, it increases HC emissions considerably. Hence, the intake temperature for FPBO+E10 tests is changed in the range of 125–200 °C.

Table 4. Fuel properties of diesel, ethanol, n-butanol, FPBO, and FPBO+E10.

Property	Unit	Diesel ^(a)	Ethanol	n-Butanol	FPBO ^(a)	FPBO+E10 ^(a)
LHV	MJ/kg	43.7	26.7	33.1	16.3	18.0
	MJ/L	35.8	21.1	26.8	19.6	20.2
Density	kg/L	0.82	0.79	0.81	1.20	1.12
C	wt%	85.5	52.2	64.8	44.4	45.1
H	wt%	13.3	13.0	13.6	7.1	8.2
O	wt%	1.1	34.8	21.6	48.2	46.5
Water	wt%	0.41	-	-	20.8	19.1
Solid	wt%	-	-	-	0.02	-
Viscosity (40 °C)	cSt	2.6	1.2	3.1	40.5	15.3
pH	-	-	-	-	2.6	-
Cetane number	-	51	8	17	-	-

^(a) Properties of Diesel, FPBO and FPBO+E10 (FPBO blended with 10 wt% ethanol) are directly measured in Ref. [9]. Therefore, the property of FPBO+E10 slightly deviates from the theoretically calculated results based on FPBO and ethanol properties.

Table 5. Experimental conditions.

Parameter	Value	
Tested fuel	Diesel	FPBO+E10
Intake temperature [°C]	50, 75, 100, 125	125, 150, 175, 200
Electrical load [kW _e]	0, 2, 3.8, 6	0, 2, 3.8
Injection timing	3 positions	

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Combustion characteristics

According to the measured needle lift, fuel pressure, and cylinder pressure profiles, the injection and combustion characteristics of diesel and FPBO+E10 are analyzed. The indicators defined in Table 3 are also discussed.

3.1.1 Effects of injection timing

At the end of the compression stroke, the pressure and temperature in engine cylinder rise sharply, and the injection timing determines the thermal conditions for the injected fuel. Therefore, injection timing plays a dominant role in fuel ignition and combustion processes, which then influences engine performance and emissions.

Figure 6. Effects of injection timing on injection and combustion processes of diesel and FPBO+E10. Electrical load is fixed at 2 kW_e . Intake temperature is fixed at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for diesel and $125 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for FPBO+E10, respectively.

In this study, 3 injection timings are tested by manually adjusting the mechanical inline pump. Figure 6 shows the needle lift, fuel pressure, cylinder pressure, and AHRR results of diesel and FPBO+E10 at these three injection timings. The electrical load is fixed at 2 kW_e , and the intake temperature is fixed at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for diesel and $125 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for FPBO+E10. Panels (a) and (b) show diesel results. the three SOI timings are -18.2 , -16.3 , and $-12.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{CA}$, respectively. The shape of the fuel pressure profile is not changed with the delayed injection timing, with the maximum fuel pressure

of around 280 bar. In panel (b), however, the peak cylinder pressure drops significantly with the delayed injection timing due to the delayed combustion event. For the chosen timings, most of energy is released after the TDC where the piston has started moving downwards, as shown in AHRR results.

FPBO+E10 results are shown in the panels (c) and (d). For FPBO+E10, three SOI timings are -19.6, -17.8, and -13.7 °CA, respectively, which are about 1.4 °CA earlier than those of diesel. Besides, FPBO+E10 has a reduced LHV compared to diesel, so the needle opening period lasts longer at the same electrical load. Interestingly, the maximum fuel pressure of FPBO+E10 reaches 370 bar, which is around 90 bar higher than diesel injection. This indicates that the responses of the mechanical pump-injector-needle system, such as SOI and peak fuel pressure, are influenced by physical fuel properties, such as the viscosity. The peak heat release rate of FPBO+E10 is obviously higher than that of diesel, while the duration is shorter.

Figure 7. Indicators of injection and combustion characteristics for diesel and FPBO+E10 at different injection timings. Other conditions are identical to those in Figure 6.

Figure 7 shows the effects of SOI on statistical indicators of injection and combustion processes. Panel (a) shows the indicators with absolute timings, including end of injection (EOI), start of combustion (SOC), combustion phasing (CP), and end of combustion (EOC), while panel (b) shows those with relative timings, including injection duration (InjD), ignition delay (ID), and burn duration (BD). Interestingly, all indicators in panel (a) rise linearly with the increase of SOI, and the slopes are very close. This means that the injection and combustion characteristics of both fuels have similar sensitivity within the tested SOI range (-20 to -12 °CA).

For diesel combustion, the SOC is around 5 °CA after the EOI, indicating that the combustion and injection process is separated. From panel (b), the ID of diesel combustion is around 14 °CA, equal to 1.56 ms at a rotation speed of 1500 rpm, which is much longer than that in modern common-rail diesel engines. In modern

common-rail diesel engine, the fuel pressure reaches around 2000 bar, leading to a large amount of entrained air, hence the injected spray completes mixing and evaporating within a shorter period. For classical diesel combustion, the AHRR profile generally includes a premixed combustion phase followed by a mixing-controlled combustion phase. However, the injection pressure of this engine is only 200–300 bar. The low injection pressure results in a reduced air entrainment, prolonging the physical atomization and evaporation processes, and consequently, the ignition delay is long. Therefore, there is just a single peak in the AHRR results as shown in panel (b) of Figure 6.

For FPBO+E10 combustion, the EOI and SOC timings are almost identical, leading to a similar InjD and ID. It is noted that the SOC timings of diesel and FPBO+E10 are almost the same, but the EOC of FPBO+E10 is much earlier, leading to the shorter burn duration of FPBO+E10. This phenomenon was also reported in previous work [10]: even though FPBO has a much lower cetane number than diesel, it burns fast if the ambient temperature meets the requirement of autoignition.

Combustion phasing (CP) is an important indicator for optimizing engine efficiency. Theoretically, the thermal efficiency is optimal when CP is exactly located at TDC (it shifts a bit to the heat-loss processes). A delayed CP means more heat is released after the piston starts moving downwards, lowering the thermal efficiency. However, an advanced CP means more heat is released during compression phase, producing negative work, or even inducing reversal of the rotation. In practice, engine CP is adjusted to be located just after TDC. As shown in Figure 7, at the same pump position, CP of diesel is about 3 °CA later than that of FPBO+E10. For this operating condition, the engine is optimized (CP=1.4 °CA after TDC) for FPBO+E10 when the inline pump is adjusted to the middle position. At this position, the CP of diesel is 4.7 °CA after TDC. This pump position is chosen to investigate the effects of electrical load and intake temperature as shown in the following sections.

3.1.2 Effects of load

The output load on crank shaft decides the amount of fuel injection. Different electrical loads are tested for diesel (0, 2, 3.8, and 6 kW_e) and FPBO+E10 (0, 2, and 3.8 kW_e). The inline pump is fixed at the middle position, and the intake temperature is fixed at 50 °C for diesel and 125 °C for FPBO+E10, respectively.

Figure 8 shows the needle lift, fuel pressure, cylinder pressure, and AHRR results of diesel and FPBO+E10 at the tested loads. The typical needle lift profile is expected to look like diesel injection at the load 6 kW_e: a sharp increase followed by a short plateau at around 0.5 mm, then a slight decrease to around 0.45 mm for some period, depending on the injection duration, and finally a fast drop to fully seated. However, in panel (a), the shape of needle lift profile for diesel injection changes significantly. This is because the injection volume of diesel at the lower load is small, owing to its high volumetric LHV. At idle and 2 kW_e, the injection is finished before the fuel pressure reaches the maximum pressure (around 330 bar), and consequently, the needle does not reach the fully open position, and the maximum lift is reduced. In panel (c), however, in the needle opening phase of FPBO+E10 injection, the fuel pressure profiles as well as needle lift profiles overlap at different loads. The change in electrical loads only affects the timing of needle

closing. It is noted that in all needle lift profiles, there is a small spike towards negative at 8 °CA after TDC. It is a mechanical design of the original engine to force the injection to stop ultimately at this moment. However, due to the lower volumetric LHV of FPBO+E10, a longer injection duration would be needed to reach 6 kW_e load. In the future, more modifications on the injection system will be implemented to solve this problem.

Figure 8. Effects of electrical load on injection and combustion processes of diesel and FPBO+E10. Intake temperature is fixed at 50 °C for diesel and 125 °C for FPBO+E10, respectively.

The shape of needle lift also influences the AHRR profiles. For FPBO combustion, the peak of AHRR rises and is slightly delayed with the increase of load. But for diesel combustion, since the maximum needle lift increases at higher load, the phase of peak AHRR is almost unchanged in the load range of 0–3.8 kW_e.

Figure 9 shows the statistical indicators. As discussed above The CP of diesel is almost unchanged at different loads, while the CP of FPBO+E10 delays with increasing load. Another interesting phenomenon is that the EOC timing for FPBO+E10 is delayed with increasing load, while the EOC timing for diesel seems unchanged in the load range of 2–6 kW_e. The main reason is the difference in injection duration. For diesel, the ignition delay is longer than the injection duration. Hence there is no obvious mixing-controlled combustion.

For FPBO+E10, however, the ignition delay is shorter than the injection duration at 3.8 kW_e. Theoretically, the AHRR profile is expected to contain a mixing-controlled combustion phase, in which the combustion reaction rate is limited by the mixing of injected fuel. However, we cannot distinguish the obvious mixing-controlled

combustion phase from the AHRR profiles. The presumable cause for a lack of mixing-controlled combustion is the short injection duration combined with the long ignition delay due to the low injection pressure.

Figure 9. Indicators of injection and combustion characteristics for diesel and FPBO+E10 at different electrical loads. Other conditions are same to Figure 8.

3.1.3 Effects of intake temperature

The autoignition of FPBO+E10 requires a high ambient temperature in the engine cylinder. Hence, different intake temperatures are tested, 50–125 °C for diesel and 125–200 °C for FPBO+E10, respectively. Electrical load is fixed at 2 kW_e.

Figure 10 shows the needle lift, fuel pressure, cylinder pressure, and AHRR profiles. Figure 11 shows the statistical indicators. As expected, intake temperature has negligible influence on fuel injection processes.

For diesel combustion, it is found that the increased intake temperature cannot decrease the ignition delay. This could be because instead of chemical delay, the physical delay dominates the total ignition delay time at tested conditions, including droplet breakup, atomization, mixing and evaporation. The increased intake temperature could improve evaporation, but the intake density is reduced at the same time (natural aspiration), which influences atomization and mixing.

For FPBO+E10, the increased intake temperature from 125 to 200 °C does shorten ignition delay from 14 to 12.5 °CA after TDC. The combustion phasing is also advanced slightly.

Figure 10. Effects of intake temperature on injection and combustion processes of diesel and FPBO+E10. Electrical load is fixed at 2 kW_e .

Figure 11. Indicators of injection and combustion characteristics for diesel and FPBO+E10 at different intake temperatures. Other conditions are same to Figure 10.

3.1.4 Combustion stability

Combustion stability is important to the genset engine, which affects the working life span and the grid stability. The coefficient of variance (COV) of the nIMEP is employed to evaluate engine combustion stability. COV_{nIMEP} is defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean value of the nIMEP, averaged from 125 consecutive cycles. Generally, it is recognized that stable combustion occurs when the COV_{nIMEP} value is within 5%.

Figure 12. Coefficient of variance for diesel and FPBO+E10 at different operation conditions.

Figure 12 shows the results of COV_{nIMEP} at different conditions. Unfortunately, it is higher than 5% for both diesel and FPBO+E10 at all tested cases. This is because the single-cylinder engine is modified from a 3-cylinder engine and the injector is manufactured in-house. Electrical load is the dominant factor for combustion stability. COV_{nIMEP} is higher than 10% at idle load, while it is below 8% when the load rises to over 2 kW_e. Intake temperature only has insignificant influences except at idle load.

3.2 Engine efficiencies

In this section, the results of engine mechanical efficiency ($\eta_{mechanical}$), fuel consumption rate, net indicated efficiency (η_{NIE}), and brake efficiency (η_{brake}) are presented and discussed.

As mentioned in Section 2.2.4, engine operation condition has negligible influence on the mechanical efficiency. Therefore, the results of nIMEP and BMEP at different test conditions are presented in Figure 13. A relationship between nIMEP and BMEP is built through linear regression: $nIMEP = 1.2015 * BMEP + 3.1387$. This expression indicates that:

- The $\eta_{mechanical}$ of this single-cylinder engine is the reciprocal of the slope (83.2%), lower than that of modern diesel engines (around 90%). This is

- caused by the extra friction losses (from piston rings, connecting rods, valves, and crankshaft) in the two inactive cylinders.
- The intercept of over 3 bar means that a large amount of indicated work is consumed by the parasitic components of the genset, such as the fuel pump and electrical generator.

Figure 13. Relationship between nIMEP and BMEP for all tested cases.

Figure 14 and Figure 15 show the indicated specific fuel consumption (ISFC) and net indicated efficiency (η_{NIE}) of diesel and FPBO+E10 at different loads and intake temperatures. The filled contour maps are made on the refined (5x) load and temperature coordinates, and the test conditions are marked by red dots. It is noted that for diesel tests, the results at the highest load as well as the highest intake temperature are not available since the exhaust temperature exceeded the safety level at this test condition.

The ISFC and η_{NIE} have the similar trends. When the engine runs on diesel, the highest η_{NIE} (49.1%) is at the middle load (4 kW_e) and the low intake temperature (50 °C), which corresponds to the lowest ISFC of 172 g/kW·h. This means the intake preheating is unnecessary for diesel combustion. However, compared with diesel, the η_{NIE} is generally higher when the engine runs on FPBO+E10. It is clear that a higher intake temperature is desired at higher load. The highest η_{NIE} (53.6%) is at the middle load (2 kW_e) and the higher intake temperature (175 °C), with an ISFC of 373 g/kW·h.

Figure 16 shows the brake efficiency (η_{brake}) of diesel and FPBO+E10. The maximum η_{brake} is just around 20%, and it is a function of the electrical load. This is because a large amount of indicated work is internally consumed by parasitic components and the engine could reach only 60% of the rated load after modification.

In the SmartCHP project, one of the technical objectives is to achieve a brake efficiency of over 40% at an engine load of 80%. It is expected to be achieved in the optimized 4-cylinder prototype when avoiding the possible causes for power degradation found with the single cylinder setup.

Figure 14. Indicated specific fuel consumption (ISFC) for diesel (left) and FPBO+E10 (right) at different electrical loads and intake temperatures.

Figure 15. Net indicated efficiency (NIE) for diesel (left) and FPBO+E10 (right) at different electrical loads and intake temperatures.

Figure 16. Brake efficiency for diesel (left) and FPBO+E10 (right) at different electrical loads and intake temperatures.

3.3 Exhaust gas emissions

Figure 17 shows the global lambda (excess air coefficient) and indicated specific emissions (ISCO, ISHC, and ISNO_x) for diesel and FPBO+E10 at different loads and intake temperatures.

Figure 17. Global lambda and indicated specific emissions of diesel and FPBO+E10. Global lambda: (a) and (b). ISCO: (c) and (d). ISHC: (e) and (f). ISNO_x: (g) and (h).

Global lambda is the ratio of actual air-fuel ratio to the stoichiometric value. The diesel engine typically applies lean combustion, which means $\lambda > 1$. For diesel engine with natural aspiration, the volume of air inhaled in each intake stroke is almost constant, while its mass is strongly influenced by the intake temperature. For a given intake temperature, the injected fuel mass in each cycle, depending on the load, dominates the global lambda. Compared to diesel, the global lambda for FPBO+E10 is slightly higher at the same load, owing to the fuel oxygen content. For diesel combustion, with loads lower than 6 kW_e, the global lambda decreases to below 1.4. This is the lower limit before excessive soot formation will occur and in practice defines the maximum power. This explains the reason for power degradation to some extent: the intake mass flow is not sufficient for more injected fuel at higher load.

ISCO of diesel and FPBO+E10 is at a low level of around 0.5 g/kW·h, except for diesel combustion at high load. When lambda approaches 1, the decrease in oxygen content influences the conversion from CO to CO₂, leading to a higher CO emission.

Diesel and FPBO+E10 have comparable ISHC levels. In-cylinder temperature has an important effect on HC emission. The increased intake temperature lowers ISHC, while at idle load, the lower in-cylinder temperature results in a higher HC emission.

NO_x forms at high-temperature, oxygen-rich regions. Owing to the intake preheating, the level of NO_x emissions is quite high in this modified diesel genset. The lowest NO_x emissions are over 6 g/kW·h. Therefore, it is necessary to install an aftertreatment system, e.g., a selective catalytic reduction (SCR) device.

In general, FPBO+E10 has comparable emission levels with diesel. At the same intake temperature (125 °C), FPBO+E10 has slightly higher CO and HC emissions but around half NO_x emissions compared to diesel.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a modified single-cylinder diesel genset engine is employed to investigate the engine performance running on FPBO. The engine working principle and operating procedure are detailed. The needle lift, fuel pressure, and cylinder pressure data are collected for evaluating fuel injection and combustion characteristics. Fuel consumption rate and exhaust emissions are measured to analyze engine performance. Diesel is used as a reference fuel and FPBO blended with 10% ethanol is tested. The influences of injection timing, electrical load (0–6 kW_e for diesel and 0–3.8 kW_e for FPBO+E10), and intake temperature (50–125 °C for diesel and 125–200 °C for FPBO+E10) are studied. The main findings from this study are:

- For the same settings of the mechanical inline pump, the injection duration of FPBO+E10 is almost doubled compared to diesel, the start of injection is slightly earlier, and the maximum injection pressure is higher.
- The 'typical' mixing-controlled combustion phase is not observed for both diesel and FPBO+E10 at all tested cases. The injection and combustion events do not overlap, even at a high load.
- With the retarded start of injection timing (in the range of -20 to -12 °CA after TDC), the start of combustion, combustion phasing, and end of combustion are almost linearly delayed with a similar sensitivity for both diesel and FPBO+E10.
- The autoignition of FPBO+E10 requires a high in-cylinder temperature. In the tested cases, the ignition delay of FPBO+E10 is close to that of diesel, while the burn duration of FPBO+E10 is much shorter.
- For the engine running on FPBO+E10, higher engine loads slightly delay the combustion phasing, while higher intake temperatures shorten the ignition delay.
- Running on diesel, the optimized engine net indicated efficiency is 49.1% at the load of 4 kW_e and intake temperature of 50 °C, with the indicated specific fuel consumption of 172 g/kW·h. For FPBO+E10, the net indicated efficiency reaches 53.6% at a load of 2 kW_e and intake temperature of 175 °C, with the indicated specific fuel consumption of 373 g/kW·h. For this set-up the brake efficiency is only 20%. This is due to the conversion of the engine to a single cylinder, leading to relatively high parasitic losses.
- The pollutant emissions of FPBO+E10 are comparable to that of diesel. At the same intake temperature (125 °C) and load, FPBO+E10 has slightly higher CO and HC emissions but around half of the NO_x emissions of diesel.

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